

Normal heart rate amperage, a new diagnostic tool for rapid synthetic analysis

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Abstract

In this small work, a new way of percentage accessing the tendency of a fateful outcome in relation to cardiac electrophysiology is suggested, for evaluation in a small decision Δt , on the course of an arrhythmic degeneration based on a simple criterion, of amperage evaluation. of the heartbeat. For the success of the proposal, the line integral of the vector force field corresponding to the normal electrocardiogram tracing was calculated, at its upper limit of normality. Next, it was proposed to use a new mathematical derivative of application for multiple variables when the variables involved tend to values close to each other.

Introduction

There is no source in the literature that explains the normal amperage value of the normal heartbeat. But a detailed analysis of mathematical-physical nature, of the behavior of the force field from the normal electrocardiogram, at the upper limit of normality, can raise enough data to establish, at the time or by future academic incursions, a parameter of normality or comparison with the abnormality, of this fundamental unit of electrical physics or cardiac electrophysiological biophysics, in the sense of having one more data at the service of cardiologists in order to have in hand a synthetic data, fast and easy to evaluate, of the electrical behavior of the heart .

A mathematical foray of approach known as line integral of a vector field of forces, allows to obtain the value in amperes, from the electrocardiogram tracing, and to conclude by the existence of an upper limit value of normality in which it is considered that when value corresponding to the work in meV, of a normal heartbeat, for which there are no repercussions in the conduction of the nervous stimulus that means a deterioration of the concatenated and coordinated electrical events,

which culminate in an effective cardiac muscle contraction. In the same way that it is inferred that a high amperage can deteriorate the transmission of the cardiac impulse, it can be concluded that an amperage generated by the very stimulus of the nerve centers, pacemakers, or not, of the heart must operate within limits that enable the conduction circuit of the electrical stimulus operate within a range that does not damage the heart muscle or that interferes with its generation and / or propagation along the muscle tissue. There would then be a threshold from which, the nerve bundles would become inappropriate for the conduction of the stimulus. This threshold would correspond to the threshold for which the external discharge on the heart would generate an interference in the conductance of the contractile stimulus, when then the collapse of the contractile mechanisms would be affected in order to create a rupture in the continuity of the electrical transmission. In this way, using the mathematical relationships abstracted from the data that an electrocardiogram can provide, the possibility of creating a new parameter for comparing any electrocardiographic tracing with a pre-established normality value, from which it can be extract an index of tendency to electro-mechanical collapse of the cardiac conduction system.

The laborious complexity of the calculation only becomes viable when we consider the advances in the area of information technology, which allow the development of algorithms, which when applied, the computational analysis of an electrocardiographic record allows to obtain the referred value, both for normality and for the trend expressed by the rate of variation of the parameters obtained from any electrocardiogram in relation to a higher borderline value of normality, thus obtaining a reference of tendency from normality to abnormality, which may well be useful in emergency situations, in the sense to obtain an instant overview of the severity of an electrophysiological cardiological event.

ECG trace

Line integral of the vector strength field of the electrocardiogram tracing at the upper limit of normality

$$y = x^2$$

$$X=t$$

$$Y=t^2$$

$$A=(0,0) \quad B=(1.5,2.5) \quad \vec{v} \cong \overrightarrow{AB} = B - A = (1.25,2.5) - (0,0) = (1.25,2.5) \quad t \in [0,1.25]$$

$$r(t) = t\vec{i} + t^2\vec{j} \quad r'(t) = 1\vec{i} + 2t\vec{j}$$

$$\int_a^b \vec{F}r(t) * r'(t)dt \quad f(x,y) = (y,x) \rightarrow \int_0^{1.5} (-t^2, t)(1,2t)dt \rightarrow \int_0^{1.5} (-t^2 + 2t^2)dt$$

$$\int_0^{1.5} t^2 dt = \frac{t^3}{3} \Rightarrow \frac{1.5^3}{3} - \frac{0^3}{3} = 1.125$$

$$AB+BC=1.125+1.125=2.25$$

For the point T of the ecg graph, changing the values of the curve

$$y = x^2$$

$$X=t$$

$$Y=t^2$$

$$A=(0,0) \quad B=(2,15) \quad \vec{v} \equiv \overrightarrow{AB} = B - A = (2,15) - (0,0) = (2,15) \quad t \in [0,2]$$

$$r(t) = t\vec{i} + t^2\vec{j} \quad r'(t) = 1\vec{i} + 2t\vec{j}$$

$$\int_a^b \vec{F} r(t) * r'(t) dt \quad f(x,y) = (y,x) \rightarrow \int_0^2 (-t^2, t)(1, 2t) dt \rightarrow \int_0^2 (-t^2 + 2t^2) dt$$

$$\int_0^2 t^2 dt = \frac{t^3}{3} \Rightarrow \frac{2^3}{3} - \frac{0^3}{3} = 2.66$$

$$AB+BC=2.66+2.66 = 5.32$$

QRS complex:

A(0,0) B(0.5,1) c(1,0) (Q wave)

$$\int \vec{F} dr = \int_{c_1} \vec{F} dr + \int_{c_2} \vec{F} dr$$

$$C_1 \quad x=x_1+at \quad \vec{v} = \overrightarrow{AB} = B - A \rightarrow (0.5,1) - (0,0) = \vec{v} = (0.5,1)$$

$$Y=y_1+bt$$

$$X=0-0.5t$$

$$Y=0+t$$

$$\vec{r}(t) = 0 - 0.5t\vec{i} + 0.5 + t\vec{j}$$

$$X=0 \Rightarrow -0.5t$$

$$X=0.5 \quad t \in [0,0.5]$$

$$\int_a^b \vec{F} r(t) * r'(t) dt \rightarrow (0 + t, 0 - 0.5t) * (0.5, 1) dt$$

$$\int_0^1 0 dt = 0$$

C2 $x=x_1+at$

$$Y=y_1+bt \quad \vec{v} = \overrightarrow{BC} = C - B \Rightarrow \vec{v} = (1,0) - (1,0.5) = (0, -0.5)$$

$$\vec{r}(t) = 0\vec{i} + 1 - 0.5t\vec{j}$$

$$R'(t) = -0.5\vec{i} + 0\vec{j}$$

$$X=0.5-0.5t=0 \rightarrow x=1$$

$$Y=1-0.5t=0 \rightarrow y=1-0.5t$$

$$X=0.5=1$$

$$X=1=0 \quad t \in [1,0]$$

$$\int_1^0 Fr(t) * r'(t) dt = \int_1^0 (1 - 0.5t, 1) * (-0.5, 0) = \int_1^0 -0.5 + 0.25t + 0 dt \Rightarrow$$

$$0.25 \int_1^0 -2t + 0.25 \int_1^0 \frac{t^2}{2}$$

$$= -0.5 + \frac{1}{4} = -0.5 - 0.0625 = -0.5625$$

S wave= $A'(0,0) B'(0.5,2) C'(0,0.8)$

$$\int \vec{F} dr = \int_{c_1} \vec{F} dr + \int_{c_2} \vec{F} dr$$

C1 $x=x_1+at$

$$Y=y_1+bt \quad \vec{v} = \overrightarrow{A'B'} = B' - A' = (0.5,2) - (0,0) = \vec{v} = (0.5,2)$$

$$\vec{r}(t) = 1 - 0.5t\vec{i} + 1 + 2t\vec{j} \quad , \quad r'(t) = 1.5$$

$$X=0 \rightarrow 1-0.5t=0 \rightarrow t=2$$

$$X=0.5 \rightarrow t=1 \quad t \in [2,1]$$

$$\int_a^b Fr(t) * r'(t) = (0 + 2t, 0 - 0.5t) * (0.5, 2) dt = 0.0 + t + 1 - t dt = 0 \rightarrow \int_2^1 0 dt = 0$$

C2 $x=x_1+at$

$$Y=y_1+bt \quad \vec{v} = \overrightarrow{B'C'} = C' - B' = (0,0.8) - (0.5,2) = \vec{v} (-0.5,-1.2)$$

$$X=0.5-at$$

$$Y=2-bt \quad x=0.5+0.5t \Rightarrow x=0.5 \Rightarrow t=0$$

$$Y=2+1.2t \Rightarrow y=0 \Rightarrow t=-2/1.2 \quad t \in [0, -\frac{2}{1.2}]$$

$$r(t)=0.5+0.5t\vec{i} + 2 + 1.2t\vec{j} \quad r'(t) = 0.5 + 1.2$$

$$\int_0^{-2/1.2} Fr(t) * r'(t) dr = (0.5 + 0.5t, 2 + 1.2t)(0.5, 1.2) dt$$

$$\rightarrow 0.5 * (0.5 + 0.5t) + 1.2 * (2 + 1.2t) dt =$$

$$> 0.25 + 0.25t + 2.4 + 1.2 - 2.4t dt =$$

$$> \left(0.25 + \frac{0.25t^2}{2} + 2.4 + 1.2 \right) - 2 * \frac{4t^2}{2} = (3.25 - (-3.30)) = 6.55$$

$$A(0,0) \quad B(0.75,19) \quad C(1.5,0)$$

$$\int \vec{F} dr = \int_{c1} \vec{F} dr + \int_{c2} \vec{F} dr$$

$$C1 \quad x=x_1+at$$

$$Y=y_1+bt \\ (0.75,19)$$

$$\vec{v} = \overrightarrow{AB} = B - A = (0.75,19) - (0,0) = \vec{v} =$$

$$X=0+0.75t$$

$$Y=0+19t \quad x=0 \rightarrow t=0 \quad x=0.75/19=0.03847$$

$$\vec{r}(t) = 0.75t\vec{i} + 19t\vec{j}$$

$$\vec{r}'(t) = 0.75 + 19 = 19.75$$

$$\int_a^b Fr(t) * r'(t) dt = (0.75t, 19t) * (0.75, 19) = 0.5625t + 361t dt$$

$$\int_0^{0.038} \frac{0.5625t^2}{2} + \frac{361t^2}{2} = \frac{361.5625t^2}{2} = 7.79 * 10^{-4}$$

$$C2 \quad x=x_1+at \quad B(0.75,19) \quad C(1.5,0)$$

$$Y=y_1+bt \quad \vec{v} = \overline{BC} = B - C = (0.75 - 1.5)(19 - 0) = (-0.75, 19)$$

$$X=-0.75+0.75t$$

$$Y=19+19t \quad x=0.75 \rightarrow t=2$$

$$X=19 \rightarrow t=0 \quad t \in [2,0]$$

$$\vec{r}(t) = -0.75 + 0.75t\vec{i} + 19 + 19t\vec{j}$$

$$\vec{r}'(t) = 0.75 + 19$$

$$\int_2^0 (-0.75 + 0.75t, 19 + 19t)(0.75, 19) dt$$

$$= -0.5625 + 0.5625t + 14.25 + 14.25t dt \Rightarrow \int_2^0 13.6875 + \frac{14.81t^2}{2} = 13.6875 - 15.93 = -2.25$$

$$C1+c2=-2.25+7.79*10^{-4}=-2.25$$

(4);(5)

Total meV=16.37 corresponding to the sum of all results

Calculating the total electron volts per time in seconds= 16.37/1000
=0.016 /0.32 seconds=0.05 eV per second .

Converting to amperage=0.2 mA (miliAmpere) for one heart beat.

Considering in one minute of heart beats the total equals 12 mA, but if we consider the total heart rate of a fibrillation at 300 plus beats, it equals 60 mA the we can calculate what would be the amperage of a single beat at fibrillation dividing the total mA of a fibrillation by the normal rate of heart beats at 60 beats per minute then it is possible to conclude that the variance of the single heart beat from 0.2 mA to 1 mA (total fibrillation mA by the normal heart rate), which could lead us to conjecture that the amperage measure might be Worth a trial for its validity to predict when a heart beat will degenerate in to fibrillation, additionally we can provide a synthetic parameter to evaluate the total net charge of a healthy individual or its tendency to degenarated rityhms from the simple evaluation of its amperage. Eventhough a rather complex calculus that demands time, could be turned into na algorithm that offered the amperage for heart beats as simple tool for evaluating the electropysiological enviroment of the impulse conduction as a first evaluation parameter.

The cirunstances that surrounds the values of the above calculus and the the check for its certainty, can be ameliorated if we compare with the known parameters used in defibrillators devices at its mean value of voltage in operation, and the corresponding sensations a person might feel when applied a certain amperage. So considering the highest value for the resistance of the human body in Ohms at 100000 Ohms, with a chok of 200 volts, for the calculated value of electron ovltis per heart beat it would result in a correponding 25 volts of charge above the value of the charge of the heart, corresponding to 100 mA which is the given value for the operation of a defibrilator in certain manuals, delivered to the heart of that given value of schok.(1)

1 mA = 0.001 AMP (short for amperes) Amps are referred to as CURRENT. Resistor values are in OHMS (Ω is the symbol for ohms)

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E stands for **volts**, I stands for amps, and R stands for resistance.

If your control circuit is using a 250Ω resistor:

mA	Amps x Resistance	Volts
4	0.004 x 250Ω	1

The NIOSH states "Under dry conditions, the **resistance** offered by the **human body** may be as high as 100,000 ohms. Wet or broken skin may drop the **body's resistance** to 1,000 ohms," adding that "high-voltage **electrical energy** quickly breaks down **human skin**, reducing the **human body's resistance** to 500 ohm (3)

"The body has *resistance* to current flow. More than 99% of the body's resistance to electric current flow is at the skin. Resistance is measured in ohms. A calloused, dry hand may have more than 100,000 Ω because of a thick outer layer of dead cells in the stratum corneum. The internal body resistance is about 300 Ω , being related to the wet, relatively salty tissues beneath the skin." (6)

(7)

Considering the limiar fo the current of the heart it can be calculated the referred amperage of the action potential of the heart muscle stimulus when the resistance considered is 250 Ohms to be equal 0.25 mA, but if you correct it to the internal resistance of 300 Ohms it will be equal 1.2 volts for every 6 mA, instead of being the propotion equal to 4 mA to 1 mA (3) ,so there woould be a correction for the value encountered in this work to be precisely equal to that of the potential of action (in positive values) of the hear muscle, but now measured through the lines of force of the integral of line of the vector field from the ECG trace.

In addition to what has been described there follows a new application for a new form of derivative that can be applied to multiple variables that tend to have equal values, by definition of derivative. There follows a slight demonstration and proof of the validity of the new way of solving a derivative, against proof of the value of the anti-derivative, by the sum of Rieman and using an online mathematics program (Wolfram alpha), and then the proposal to use some normal parameters and to be measured, to obtain an index that numerically signifies the tendency towards abnormality, that is, correlated values of voltages in relation to time that can translate a greater or lesser tendency towards fibrillation.

Interpret x_1 and x_2 as x_1 and x_2

$$\lim_{x_1 \rightarrow h} \frac{f(x_1+h)-f(x_1)}{h} \Rightarrow \frac{f(x_1+h)-f(h)}{h} = \frac{f(x_1+h)-f(x_1)}{h}$$

$$hx_1 + h^2 - h^2 = hx_1 + h^2 - hx_1 \Rightarrow -h^2 = -hx_1 \Rightarrow x_1 = h$$

$$\frac{f(x_1+h)-f(x_2)}{f(x_2)} = \frac{f(x_1+h)-f(x_2)}{f(x_2)} \Rightarrow x_1h + h^2 - hx_2 - hx_2 = 0 \Rightarrow x_1h + h^2 - 2hx_2 = 0 \Rightarrow$$

$$h * (x_1 + h - 2x_2) = 0 \therefore x_1 + h - 2x_2 = 0 \leftrightarrow x_1 = 2x_2 \text{ when } h \rightarrow 0$$

$x_1=h \Rightarrow x_1=x_2-x_1$ for $x_1=2x_2 \Rightarrow x_1=-x_2 \Rightarrow$ if $x_2-x_1=0$ then $x_1=x_2$ then $x_2-x_1=x_2-(-x_2) \Rightarrow x_2-x_1=2x_2$
or $-x_1=x_2$ so $x_2-x_1=h=x_2-(-x_2)=2x_2 \Rightarrow 2x_2=h \rightarrow 0$, $x_2=\text{any number}$

Then :

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} x \frac{f(t+x)-f(t)}{x}, \text{ for } t=x \text{ or } t \rightarrow x \text{ can be written as } \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} x \frac{f(t+x)-f(x)}{x} \text{ so if I consider}$$

$$\frac{r_1 * s_1}{g_1}(t) = \frac{r_2 * s_2}{g_2}(x)$$

The division of the inverse of the product of the terms will express the derivative of a multivariable interdependent equation as like:

$$g_2 * r_1 * s_1 = g_1 * r_2 * s_2 \Rightarrow \frac{g_2 * r_1 * s_1}{g_1 * r_2 * s_2}$$

$$\text{Proof : } \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} x \frac{f(t+x)-f(t)}{x} \text{ substituting for } t = \frac{r_1 * s_1}{g_1} \quad x = \frac{r_2 * s_2}{g_2} =$$

$$\frac{\frac{r_1 * s_1}{g_1} + \frac{r_2 * s_2}{g_2} - \frac{r_2 * s_2}{g_2}}{\frac{r_2 * s_2}{g_2}} = \frac{g_2 * r_1 * s_1 + g_1 * r_2 * s_2 - g_1 * r_2 * s_2}{\frac{r_2 * s_2}{g_2}} = \frac{r_1 * s_1}{g_1} * \frac{g_2}{r_2 * s_2} = \frac{\frac{r_1 * s_1}{g_1}}{\frac{r_2 * s_2}{g_2}} \rightarrow t/x$$

Proof by antiderivative:

Rewriting the given definition of an integral by the Riemann Sum as:

$$\int_x^t \frac{t}{x} dx = \lim_{t \rightarrow x} \sum_{t=x}^x \frac{t-x}{t} * \frac{t}{x} \implies \text{it gives the following result:}$$

$$\sum \frac{x y z - n^3 x y z}{n^3 x y z} \text{ where } n = 3$$

$$\sum -\frac{26}{27}$$

$$\int \frac{10 \times 5 \times 2 - 3^3 \times 10 \times 5 \times 2}{3^3 \times 10 \times 5 \times 2} dx = -\frac{26x}{27} + \text{constant}$$

So you can apply a rule of comparison between the normal (known) and the measured and check the distance from the expected normal values:

Ev1 = Electron volts normal

T1 = beats in 1 minute

Δt_1 = total duration of all stimuli measured in waves

Ev2 = Electron volts measured

T2 = beats in 1 minute measured

Δt_2 = total duration of all stimuli measured in measured waves

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow x} \frac{\left(\frac{Ev1T1}{\Delta t1}\right)(t)}{\left(\frac{Ev2T2}{\Delta t2}\right)(x)} = \frac{t}{x}$$

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} x \frac{f(t+x)-f(t)}{x} \text{ substituting for } t = \frac{Ev1T1}{\Delta t1} \quad x = \frac{Ev2T2}{\Delta t2} = t/x$$

Values below 1 = higher risk of fibrillation the lowest the value , near 0.0

$r1 = \text{RandomReal}[0.016] \rightarrow Ev1$
 $r2 = \text{RandomReal}[0.016] \rightarrow Ev2$
 $g1 = 0.32 \rightarrow \Delta t1$
 $g2 = 0.32 \rightarrow \Delta t2$
 $s2 = 60 \rightarrow T2$
 $s1 = 60 \rightarrow T1$
 $a = (r1 * s1) / g1$
 $b = (r2 * s2) / g2$
 $y = (g2 * r1 * s1) / (g1 * r2 * s2)$

As a way of simplicity and adaptaion to the forumula, I used the relation of the voltage to time and heart beat, but it indirectly relates to the amperage.

Miscelaneous: table of sensetivity to mA (miliamperage) for comparison.

Current level in milliamperes	Probable effect on the human body
1 mA	Tingling sensations and a change in perception levels.
5 mA	A subtle shock. The individual is able to let go of the object. Intense involuntary spasms might lead to injury.
6-16 mA	A painful shock. Loss of muscular control. Often referred to as a freezing current where the individual cannot separate from the electrical source.
17-99 mA	Extreme pain, lung failure, strong muscular contractions. Inability to separate from electrical source. Possibly fatal.
100-2000 mA	Severely abnormal heartbeat. Extreme muscular contractions and nerve damage occur. Likely resulting in death.
>2,000 mA	Heart stops beating, internal organs are severely damaged and extreme burns. Probable death.

(2)

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